

Multiscalar non-motorized street network types

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1. Introduction

This document presents the full Extract, Transform, and Load (ETL) workflow for generating multiscalar non-motorized street network types, based on the methodology developed by Berghauser Pont et al. (2019), Serra (2014), and Gil and Serra (2017). Using a line-segment representation of the street network to compute angular betweenness, the method produces representative street network types that capture the performance of non-motorized streets across multiple spatial scales within the city. This is a general and reproducible protocol. The examples included in this document (with full implementation details available on [GitHub](#)) are based on a specific set of cities used for demonstration purposes. However, the same workflow can be applied to other datasets, including a smaller number of cities or a single city. Users are encouraged to adapt the protocol to their own research context and needs.

2. Extracting, Transform, and Load (ETL)

ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) is a process that moves data from sources to targets through transformations. It involves extracting data, cleaning it, conforming it, and loading it into the target system (Figure 1).

Figure 1: ETL process.

For this protocol, the street network, the main dataset, is retrieved from the OpenStreetMap (OSM) database. The network is then transformed into a line-segment representation to compute angular betweenness, before being clustered and loaded into the database (Figure 2).

Figure 2: ETL process for this project.

2.1. Extracting

The street network is extracted from the OpenStreetMap (OSM) database using OSMnx in Python with specific parameters. OSMnx is an open-source Python library that enables the downloading, modelling, analysis, and visualisation of street networks, public transport networks, parcels, buildings, and other geospatial features across cities, regions, and countries (Boeing, 2017). Instructions for reproducing this step are available in the script accessible via this repository on [GitHub](#).

Libraries Requirement

To retrieve the OSMnx data, begin by importing the necessary libraries into your script. For this step, the following libraries were utilized:

High- Level Requirements

Library	Version
OSMnx	1.2.2
NetworkX	2.8.5
GeoPandas	0.14.3

Low- Level Requirements

Library	Version
Matplotlib	3.9.0
SQLAlchemy	1.4.40

Input Requirement

There are different ways to retrieve street network data using OSMnx (see the [User Guide](#) for further details). In this protocol, predefined boundaries based on the official administrative limits of the example cities were used.

As a rule of thumb, the predefined boundary needs to include a buffer zone as large as the largest radius of analysis around the city/region in question. In this case, as will be described in Section 2.1.3, the largest analysis radius is 5km (Figure 3). This buffer zone is required to avoid 'edge effects' (Gil, 2017).

Figure 3: administrative limits and boundaries for each city.

Access the Non-motorized Street Network Data

To obtain the non-motorized street network data from the OSM database, you must set some parameters for the OSMnx library methods. In this work, the parameters used are:

- `network_type='all'`: Specifies the type of road network to retrieve. Options include 'all' (default), 'drive', 'walk', 'bike', 'drive_service', 'walk_service', and 'bike_service'. 'all' includes all types.
- `simplify=False`: Specifies whether the extracted network is simplified or not.
- `retain_all=True`: If True, retains all disconnected subgraphs in the downloaded graph. If False, only the largest connected subgraph is retained.

The default parameters were used for the other methods.

2.2. Transform

The transformation process consists of several phases, starting with converting the graph type of the raw network, followed by cleaning, segmenting, measuring angular betweenness, and concluding with statistical analysis. During this procedure, Python scripts and the Place Syntax Tool (PST) are used at different stages, as illustrated in Figure 4 and detailed in the subsequent sections.

Figure 4: Transformation process

2.2.1. Transform Graph Type

The raw network provided by OSMnx comes in the form of a MultiDiGraph. A MultiDiGraph is a type of graph data structure where multiple parallel edges can exist between nodes. However, this format is not suitable for segment analysis, where the direction of movement is not considered. Instead, the key is the simple connection between the nodes and the characteristics of these connections. Therefore, it is necessary to transform the OSMnx MultiDiGraph into a simple, undirected graph (Figure 5).

This step was necessary to input the non-motorised street network into the PST (see next step). So far, the PST does not perform as well with multidigraphs as it does with simple graphs.

Figure 5: difference between a MultiDiGraph and a simple Graph

After extracting the street network from OSMnx, the MultiDiGraph for each of these cities and regions was transformed into a simple Graph. This transformation was accomplished using NetworkX, a Python library designed for the creation, manipulation, and study of the structure, dynamics, and functions of complex networks.

To use NetworkX for graph transformations, it is necessary to follow the specified requirements and parameters. Instructions for reproducing this step can be found in the script accessible via repository on [GitHub](#).

Libraries Requirement

To transform the graph type, begin by importing the necessary libraries into your script. For this step, the following libraries were utilized:

High- Level Requirements

Library	Version
OSMnx	1.2.2
NetworkX	2.8.5

Low- Level Requirements

Library	Version
GeoPandas	0.14.3
Matplotlib	3.9.0
SQLAlchemy	1.4.40

Graph Transformation

To transform the graph, specific guidelines were established to ensure the elimination of redundant edges while preserving essential components. These rules are important for creating a segment map from a raw street network extracted from OSMnx. The main parameter is that if the graph has edges with the same origin and destination nodes and identical lengths, it is likely that both edges represent the same street. In this case, one of the edges can be removed, simplifying the connection to a single

edge. However, if edges share the same origin and destination nodes but have different lengths, they should be retained as they are likely to represent different streets (Figure 6). For details of how it was done, see this repository on [GitHub](#).

Figure 6: Rules to convert MultiDiGraph to a Graph

2.2.2. Filter Essential Attributes and Values

The next step following the graph transformation involves filtering specific attributes and values to creating a non-motorized street network. When the street network is retrieved from OSMnx with the parameter `network_type='all'`, it includes all types of streets in the raw geodata model. This comprehensive model needs to be filtered to retain only the necessary attributes and values for non-motorized streets. Instructions for reproducing this step can be found in the script accessible via this repository on [GitHub](#).

Libraries Requirement

To filter the necessary attributes and values, start by importing these libraries into your script:

High- Level Requirements

Library	Version
OSMnx	1.2.2
NetworkX	2.8.5

Low- Level Requirements

Library	Version
GeoPandas	0.14.3
Matplotlib	3.9.0
SQLAlchemy	1.4.40

Filter Attributes

When the raw geodata model is retrieved from OSMnx, it includes information that is not necessary for the purposes of this work. Therefore, it is essential to filter the data in two steps: first, filter the attribute columns, and second, filter the values within the selected columns. The original table contains more than 15 attributes columns, but only 8 are necessary to proceed with the protocol, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Data model for filtering process

Filter Attributes

After filtering the columns, the next step is to refine the values within the highway, service, and access columns, as defined in the OSM documentation. The highway column categorizes various types of roads and pathways. The service column provides details on specific types of service roads, identifying roads mainly used for accessing particular areas. The access column outlines the accessibility of a road, path, or area, specifying usage restrictions such as whether it is public, private, or restricted. For the column "highway," the included street classifications are 'primary', 'primary_link', 'secondary', 'secondary_link', 'tertiary', 'tertiary_link', 'residential', 'unclassified', 'pedestrian', 'living_street', and 'service'. Additionally, streets labelled 'service' without specific types, as well as those marked 'alley' or 'driveway', were included. Regarding access, entries with access types of unspecified, 'yes', 'permissive', 'destination', or 'designated' were also included (Figure 8).

Figure 8: filtering columns by values

2.2.3. Removing isolated islands

After filtering the necessary attributes and values the next step is to remove isolated islands. Isolated islands are those lines that are disconnected from the street network system, those islands can be formed by orphan lines, but also by subsystems.

Libraries Requirement

To clean the network in order to keep only the streets connected to the main system, start by importing these libraries into your script:

High- Level Requirements

Library	Version
OSMnx	1.2.2
NetworkX	2.8.5

Low- Level Requirements

Library	Version
GeoPandas	0.14.3
Matplotlib	3.9.0
SQLAlchemy	1.4.40

Remove Islands

The process of removing islands was completed in such a way that only the main system for each city was retained, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: removing islands process.

Exporting the in-between results

Exporting the intermediate results involves saving the street network map in a geospatial format for the next phase in PST. This exported street network is saved as a road-centre line (RCL).

2.2.4. Segmentation process

After the initial stage of transforming the network by cleaning and filtering it in Python, the next phases are executed in [PST](#). The first step is to segment the street network, ensuring that all the streets are segmented according to parameters presented in Figure 11.

Turner (2007) explored street segmentation to address limitations in previous street network representations. Streets are divided into segments at crossings and junctions, indicating a cognitive change of direction. In PST-generated maps, the results show street network segments and unlink points. Unlinks are segments that visually intersect on the map but do not correspond to actual crossings.

Software Requirements

To segment the network in order to proceed to segment analysis, start by preparing the software setup:

High- Level Requirements

Library	Version
QGIS	long release version
PST	v3.2.4-3.2.5

Segmenting the street network

The RCL street network is imported into QGIS in shapefile format. A segment map is then generated from this shapefile, following the trimming parameters as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: segmenting process.

2.2.5. Segment Analysis

With the segment map prepared, the next step is to analyze the segments. The measure used was '*angular betweenness*' (Berghauer Pont et al., 2019). The measurement of the betweenness for each segment was conducted to understand their performance across 10 different radii, considering the walking distance ranging from 500 meters to 5 kilometers. All the cities and the Turano region underwent the same analysis process.

Software Requirements

To replicate the analysis, please begin by configuring the software environment:

High- Level Requirements

Library	Version
QGIS	long release version
PST	v3.2.4-3.2.5

Measuring the angular betweenness

Using the segment map generated in the segmentation process step, an angular betweenness analysis was conducted according to the parameters shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Angular betweenness analysis.

2.2.6. Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis, based on the methodologies proposed by Serra (2014) and Gil and Serra (2017), is carried out in two main stages: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) followed by Cluster Analysis.

When analysing a single city, PCA is applied directly to its network, and Cluster Analysis is then performed on the resulting components to identify local street types. When multiple cities are analysed, PCA is first applied separately to each city to preserve their internal structure. The resulting outputs are then combined into a single dataset, and Cluster Analysis is applied to identify shared street types across cities.

In the [GitHub](#) repository example, multiple cities are included, but the same workflow can also be applied to a single-city case without changing the overall procedure.

Libraries Requirement

To conduct PCA and cluster analysis, begin by importing the necessary libraries into your script:

High- Level Requirements

Library	Version
Pandas	2.2.1
Geopandas	0.14.3
Numpy	1.24.1
Matplotlib	3.9.0
Seaborn	0.13.12
Scikit-learn	1.1.1

Scikit-learn-extra	0.3.0
Factor analyzer	0.4.1

Low- Level Requirements

Library	Version
SQLAlchemy	1.4.40

Data Preparation

It was necessary to distinguish dead-end streets from other streets during data preparation. Dead-end streets are those that do not connect to other streets, resulting in a betweenness centrality score of 0.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) constitutes the first step of the statistical workflow. PCA is a dimensionality-reduction technique that transforms a set of correlated variables into a smaller set of uncorrelated variables, known as principal components. The first component explains the largest proportion of variance in the data, while each subsequent component captures the maximum remaining variance under the constraint of orthogonality to the previous components (Jolliffe, 2002). In this analysis, PCA is used to reduce the dimensionality of the ten original variables. The first step is to determine the optimal number of components needed to adequately represent the dataset. For the set of cities used in this protocol, three principal components were identified as optimal. Together, they capture a substantial share of the total variance, with the first component explaining the largest share, followed by the second and third (Figure 14).

After selecting the optimal number of components, each principal component is interpreted to identify its underlying meaning. This interpretation is performed separately for each city to assess the extent to which components reflect consistent structural patterns across different urban contexts. The results show that the three principal components represent similar underlying dimensions across the cities analysed (Figure 15). For detailed information on this procedure and instructions to replicate it with other datasets, please refer to the [repository](#).

Figure 14: The first principal component explains about 80% of the variance for each city.

Figure 15: Rotated Component by city. This figure shows the interpretation of each principal component. Each principal component is rotated to enhance interpretability, indicating how data from different cities align with the underlying factors represented by the components.

Cluster Analysis

After confirming that the principal components show consistent interpretations across cities, the cluster analysis is performed. This method groups observations so that those within the same cluster are more similar to each other than to those in other clusters.

The CLARA (Clustering Large Applications) algorithm is used, as it is designed to handle large datasets efficiently by drawing multiple samples and clustering each subset. Before running the clustering, silhouette analysis is applied to determine the optimal number of clusters. The silhouette score evaluates how similar each observation is to its own cluster compared to other clusters; in this case, it indicates an optimal solution of four clusters.

Unlike the previous step, this analysis is conducted on a combined dataset of principal components from multiple cities. This allows for comparative analysis, enabling the structural characteristics of each city to be assessed relative to the broader sample. For further details and replication instructions, please refer to the code available in the [repository](#).

2.3. Load

After transformation, data and statistical features are loaded for manipulation and visualization. In this project, results were written to a SQL database but can also be exported in geodata formats for use in QGIS or similar software. The data was exported as combined data and by city and region.

Libraries Requirement

To recreate the loading process on the relational database, import the required libraries into your script:

High- Level Requirements

Library	Version
SQLAlchemy	1.4.40

Exported Results

The maps in Figure 16 display the results of the cluster analysis.

Figure 16: Cluster Analysis Results

References

- Berghauer Pont, M., Stavroulaki, G., & Marcus, L. (2019). Development of urban types based on network centrality, built density and their impact on pedestrian movement. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 46(8), 1549–1564. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2399808319852632>.
- Gil, J., & Serra, M. (2017). *street-network-typologies* [Software]. figshare. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.5044462.v1>
- Serra, M. L. L. A. (2014). *Anatomy of an emerging metropolitan territory - Towards an integrated analytical framework for metropolitan morphology* (Ph.D.).
- Stavroulaki, I., Berghauer Pont, M., Marcus, L., & Sun, K. (2020). *Spatial Morphology Lab 01. International laboratory for comparative research in urban form. Street networks, Sweden - Non-motorised network of Gothenburg*. <https://doi.org/10.5878/X49H-PV07>.
- Gil, J. (2017). Street network analysis "edge effects": Examining the sensitivity of centrality measures to boundary conditions. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 44(5), 819–836. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0265813516650678>.
- Boeing, G. (2017). OSMNX: New methods for acquiring, constructing, analyzing, and visualizing complex street networks. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 65, 126–139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2017.05.004>.
- Jolliffe, I. T. (Ed.). (2002). Introduction. In *Principal component analysis* (pp. 1–9). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/0-387-22440-8_1.